

ENDEMIC PLANTS OF THE CASPIAN COAST FLORA (IN AZERBAIJANI TERRITORY)**Elshad Gurbanov,***Baku State University, Faculty of Biology***Humira Huseynova,***Baku State University, Faculty of Biology***Zulfiyya Mammadova,***Baku State University, Faculty of Biology***Afaq Razaeva***Baku Engineering University***Abstract**

The Republic of Azerbaijan became a party to the UN Convention on Biological Diversity in 2000 in order to protect biodiversity, which includes flora, an integral part of natural resources.

In this regard, it is of great importance to study endemic species in order to preserve wild flora on the Caspian Sea coast within Azerbaijan's territory.

The diversity of flora on the Caspian Coast is due to a variety of physical-geographical, natural-historical factors, as well as the influence of distant floristic provinces on its formation.

Azerbaijan is one of the most diverse botanical and geographical regions in the Caucasus, with a variety of climates, soils, and vegetation. This diversity has led to the presence of many endemic plants on the territory of Azerbaijan, especially in the botanical and geographic regions near the Caspian Sea.

Endemic plants are important components of the local flora and are used as criteria for botanical-geographic zoning, based on taxonomic categories such as family, genus, and species. They are also used in the analysis of the endemic plant diversity in the Caucasus and Azerbaijan.

Material and Method: Some data on endemism in the region for protecting the plant world along the Caspian coast of Azerbaijan are presented in the works of researchers. Specifically, the flora of the republic includes 1,153 endemic plant species from the Caucasus, which accounts for 19.3% of the total flora, and 800 endemic species from Azerbaijan, representing 17.7% of the country's flora. The flora of the country includes 28 endemic genera and 75 subendemic genera, as well as 146 higher plant species that are either fully endemic or subendemic, accounting for 12% of Azerbaijan's total flora.

Results. A comparison of endemic plants found on the coast of the Caspian Sea with those of the flora of Azerbaijan was conducted.

Keywords: flora, endemism, area, criteria, climate change, biodiversity

From the comparison mentioned in Table 1, it was found that Q. F. Akhundov identified 240 endemics in the flora of Azerbaijan, and according to A. M. Askarov's "Red Book", 181 endemic species were identified, as well as 200 endemic plants from the International Caucasus. The number of relevant endemic species according to the literature sources was 28 (11.7%), 7 (3.9%), and it was concluded that they represent 61 (30.5%) of the total number.

The endemism of plants found in the flora of the Caspian coast was analyzed and presented in the synopsis of the flora.

In terms of the number of endemic plant species in Azerbaijan, the Asteraceae family has 11 species, the Fabaceae family has 8 species, the Scrophulariaceae has 6 species, and so on. Other families such as Brassicaceae, Chenopodiaceae, Caryophyllaceae, and

Rosaceae each have 3 species, while the Polygonaceae Juss family has only 2 species.

The flora of the Caspian coast includes endemic plants such as *Iris acutiloba*, *Quercus pedunculiflora*, *Astragalus bakuensis*, and *Centaurea hircanica*. There are 26 higher plant species belonging to 45 different families and 61 different genera in the flora.

Some examples of endemic wild plants on the Caspian coast include *Thesium maritimum*, *Calligonum bakuense*, and *Erysimum caspicum*.

Asteraceae is the most represented family in terms of number of genera, with 9 genera, followed by Fabaceae, Scrophularia - riaceae, Brassicaceae, and Chenopodiaceae - ce with 3 genera each. Caryophyllaceae, Rosaceae, and Polygonaceae each have only 2 genera.

V.C. Hajiyev, S.H. Musayev, and V.M. Alizadeh, among others, based on international categories, have identified endemic species in Azerbaijan that are distributed along the Caspian Sea coast (see Table 1).

Table 1.

International categories of endemic species in the flora of the Caspian coast.

Wild plants	Categories							
	EW	CR	EN	VU	NE	LC	DD	NT
Endemic species	–	3	4	6	40	1	5	2
Total	–	3	4	6	40	1	5	2
By quantity, in percentage	–	4,9	6,6	9,8	65,6	1,6	8,2	3,3

When examining the conservation status of plant species according to the "Red List of Endemic Plants of the Caucasus" of the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN), we find that 40 species (65.6%) are NE (Near Threatened), 6 species (9.8%) are VU (Vulnerable), 5 species (8.2%) are DD (Data Deficient), 4 species (6.6%) are EN (Endangered), 3 species (4.9%) CR (Critically Endangered), and 2 species (3.3%) belong to the LC (Least Concern) category. Additionally, we note that no endemic species classified as extinct (EW) are found in the flora of the territory.

The floristic composition of the area includes *Alnus barbata*, *Gleditsia caspica* Desf., *Pyrus hyrcana* Fed., *Nitraria komarovii*, and *Astragalus ignarius* Popov. Endemic species can be found in Azerbaijan, where plants of these species have been recorded in natural phytocenoses of Samur-Yalama and Absheron National Parks as well as Hirkan National Park. Among the endemic species mentioned, *P. hyrcana* has been included in the "Red Book of Azerbaijan".

As a result of the research, 61 plant species from the area of Azerbaijan and 43 plant species from the Caucasus have been identified in the flora of the Caspian Sea coast.

According to Table 4 in the "Red Book of the Republic of Azerbaijan", 69 endangered species out of 460 are represented in the flora of the Caspian region.

Floristic analysis of the wild flora of the Caspian coast revealed that endemic plants from the Caucasus area belong to 16 families, with 35 genera belonging to 43 species.

The most prominent families are *Asteraceae* (10 genera), *Fabaceae* (4 genera), and *Scrophulariaceae* and *Brassicaceae*, both with 3 genera each. These families account for a significant portion of the flora in the area. Additionally, there are 2 genera each from *Chenopodiaceae* and 11 other genera with 1-2 species.

Among the genera, *Asteraceae* Giseke has 12 species, *Fabaceae* Juss has 5 species, *Scrophulariaceae* Juss and *Brassicaceae* Burnett have 3 species each, *Boraginaceae* Juss has 4 species, and *Chenopodiaceae* has 3 species. Other families such as *Iridaceae*, *Salicaceae*, and *Polygonaceae* also contribute with 1-2 species each.

Endemic species of the Caucasus region include *Merendera trygyna*, *Iris musulmanica*, *Salix prinoides* Pursh, *Polygonum arenastrum*, *Atriplex fominii*, *Medicago caucasica* Vassilcz., *Centaurea transcaucasica* Sosn., and others. These species can be found in Samur-Shabran and Chala-Meadow vegetation in the Lankaran Lowland.

It is worth noting that endemic species are more abundant in the dendroflora of lowlands. Endemics found in the Talysh region are of Hirkan origin, which means they are relics from the Tertiary period.

Conclusion

It has been determined that endemic plant species from the Caucasus region are present in the flora of the Caspian coast, comprising 16 families, 35 genera, and 43 species. Additionally, there are 26 endemic species of Azerbaijan in this flora, belonging to 45 families and 61 genera.

The endemic plants from the Caucasus include the following families: *Asteraceae*, *Fabaceae*, *Scrophulariaceae*, *Brassicaceae*, *Boraginaceae* and *Chenopodiaceae*, each containing 1 to 12 species. The genera *Asteraceae* and *Fabaceae* each have 3 species, *Scrophulariaceae* has 2 species, and *Brassicaceae* and *Boraginaceae* have 2 species each. *Chenopodiaceae* has 3 species. Other families such as *Iridaceae*, *Salicaceae*, *Polygonaceae*, etc., also contribute 2 to 1 species each.

Asteraceae (11 species), *Fabaceae* (8 species), *Scrophulariaceae* (6 species), and *Brassicaceae*, *Chenopodiaceae*, *Caryophyllaceae*, and *Rosaceae* each with 3 species, as well as *Polygonaceae* with 2 species, all have between 8 and 2 species per family, according to the Red List of Endemic Plants of the Caucasus published by the International Union for Conservation of Nature.

Of these 40 species, 65.6% are classified as Near-Endangered (NE), 9.8% as Vulnerable (VU), 8.2% as Data Deficient (DD), 6.6% as Endangered (EN), 4.9% as Critically Endangered (CR), 3.3% as Not Threatened (NT), and 1.6% belong to the Least Concern category (LC).

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